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ENHANCING THE GRAMMAR COMPETENCE OF LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Annotation

In the article the stages of formation of grammatical skills in English language students across the different types of exercise. Exercises in oral language (in speaking) involve communication, communication that can be organized into speech and speech exercises, conditionally, as for the transfer of his skill needs to be formed under the conditions of approximate speech.

Key words: Grammar skills, skill formation, speech acts, speech exercises, grammar games.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ ИЗУЧАЮЩИХ ЯЗЫКИ

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются этапы формирования грамматических навыков у учеников английского языка через разные виды упражнений. Упражнения в устной речи (также в говорении) предполагают общение, коммуникацию, которая может быть организована в речевых и условно-речевых упражнениях, так как для обеспечения переноса навыка его нужно формировать в условиях, приближённых к речевым.

Ключевые слова: Грамматический навык, формирование навыка, речевые действия, речевые упражнения, грамматические игры.

ТИЛ ЎРГАНУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ГРАММАТИК КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯСИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ

Аннотация

Мақолада инглиз тили ўқувчиларида турли турдаги машқлар орқали грамматик кўникмаларни шакллантириш босқичлари кўриб чиқилади. Оғзаки нутқдаги машқлар нутқ ва шартли нутқ машқлари ёрдамида грамматик компетенцияни шаклланиш ва ривожланишини таъминлаш мумкинлиги яна бир бор ўз исботини топди.

Калит сўзлар: Грамматик маҳорат, малакани шакллантириш, нутқ ҳаракатлари, нутқ машқлари, грамматик ўйинлар.

Introduction. Grammar skill must have certain qualities. First of all, it is automation, which provides the process of skill formation with the necessary speed, integrity and smoothness, as well as the stability of the speech skill. It is not enough to automate any action, it must be made strong, stable, that is, if, for example, one aspect tense form of the verb is learned, then the second, then exercises are needed where these two forms “collide with each other”. You can achieve automation and stability, but this does not mean that a skill of the required quality has been created: it needs to be given flexibility, which is formed through the use of exercises of a certain nature. Flexibility is a vital quality to a skill. It is on this quality that the transfer is based, without which the skill remains a “thing in itself”, does not turn on in new situations.

Literature review. Any skill is based on a dynamic stereotype, that is, a thin and flexible system of temporary connections formed in the human brain. The formation of speech skills also occurs according to the laws of the formation of temporary connections. The physiology of higher nervous activity has accumulated enough data on the process of the formation of a dynamic stereotype. These data allow us to determine the conditions that make the formation of skills more successful. First, they include a pre-hearing. Its role in the formation of a dynamic stereotype is great. Perceiving foreign speech for the first time, a person “does not hear”, does not distinguish its properties, does not catch the grammatical form. He begins to hear when his attention is directed to something that corresponds to the instructions or is attracted by some way of presenting the material: intonation, pause, emphasis, emphasis. If the preliminary hearing is

organized correctly, then this contributes to the emergence of a dynamic stereotype.

The second condition for the formation of a skill is imitation in speech. Mastering speech begins with imitation of speech segments. Exercises like "Repeat after me" do not bring the desired results, as they are pronounced without any speech task. In the process of communication, such an imitation of grammatical patterns must necessarily have a speech orientation. For example:

- Is he a good person?

Yes, he is a good person...

But here the repetition is caused by reflection, the speaker, as it were, weighs this thought, and, perhaps, agrees with it, repeating in order to consider his “But”. So, the next condition for the formation of a skill is imitation in speech, imitation in the presence of a speech task.

The third condition is the same type of phrases. Mastering speech, a person usually encounters complexes of stimuli - with valuable phrases. The construction of phrases that are often repeated in speech causes a certain system in the work of the brain. When the brain perceives a signal of the same quality (a phrase of the same construction), the first impulses pass faster and are fixed more firmly. It follows that one of the conditions for successful automation should be the uniformity of phrases built on the basis of a speech sample.

The fourth condition is action by analogy in speech conditions. Speech actions can be performed by analogy with a model: visible, audible, abstractly invented and mentally representing. This sequence corresponds to the principle of increasing difficulties, and this must be taken into account when organizing exercises. So, the next condition for the

effective formation of skills is the use of actions by analogy in exercises for the assimilation of language forms.

The fifth condition is the infallibility of speech actions. It is known from psychology that it is especially important to avoid mistakes at the initial stage of mastering any action, where they turn out to be exceptionally persistent. Actions performed by the speaker himself, even those that distort the meaning, are fixed easily and firmly. Therefore, the true condition for the formation of a skill is the relative error-freeness in the performance of an action, provided by the prevention of errors. In this case, the brain receives positive reinforcement, and the dynamic stereotype of this action is established more successfully.

The sixth condition for the formation of a skill is the variety of "circumstances" of automation. "Circumstance" is the ability to transfer, which manifests itself in the fact that a student who has mastered, for example, the form of the perfect, will be able to generate phrases of the same type, but on a different material - this is the stereotype of the skill - and use them in different situational circumstances - this is its dynamism and flexibility. It is this ability that is the goal of the formation of grammatical skill.

The seventh condition is the speech nature of the exercises. Each type of speech activity should be mastered during exercises in the same type of activity. To teach speaking, the exercise must not only be oral, it must be an exercise in oral speech, in speaking. Oral can be considered any exercise performed orally (reproducing what has been memorized, reading a dialogue in pairs, transforming sentences). The student does not have a speech task, but has a formal learning task. Such speech actions can be called pronunciation, not speaking.

Research methodology. Exercises in oral speech (also in speaking) involve communication, communication, which can be organized in speech and conditional speech exercises, since in order to ensure the transfer of a skill, it must be formed in conditions close to speech.

Exercises, which are designed to be similar in nature to speech, should be based on the same principles as the process of speech communication itself.

The first principle of constructing conditional speech exercises is the principle of using the speaker's speech task. It is realized in the fact that in the exercise, when performing speech actions, the student uses those speech tasks that are characteristic of the real process of communication.

The second principle of constructing conditional speech exercises is the principle of analogy in the education and assimilation of grammatical forms. It means that the student, performing some kind of speech task, follows a certain pattern, usually presented in the teacher's remark. Giving his remarks, the student constructs them by analogy with the model, which gradually, as psychologists say, becomes the inner property of a person. This is how the so-called sense of form appears, on the basis of which a person instantly and accurately forms any similar form.

Consequently, the second principle of constructing conditional speech exercises ensures the assimilation of the grammatical form, that is, the design of a speech unit. The first principle - the principle of using the speaker's speech task - is designed to provide the functional side of speech, that is, the call of the model.

Therefore, the third principle of constructing conditional speech exercises is the principle of parallel assimilation of the grammatical form and its function in speech.

These principles allow the use of exercises that would create optimal conditions for the formation of grammatical skills. Grammar skill building exercises should:

1) be situational (this means phrases (the teacher's remarks and the student's reaction) are pronounced only when it corresponds to the situation, either natural or specially created);

2) to provide at least a conditional motivation for the student's reaction, to be pronounced not for the sake of any grammatical task, but in the presence of the speaker's speech task;

3) to ensure in each of the student's remarks the regular repetition of the same type of phrases with an automated form;

4) ensure that the student's voluntary attention is predominantly focused on the purpose and content of the statement, and not on its form;

5) to ensure the relative faultlessness of the student's actions, which can be achieved by the appropriate organization of exercises;

6) imitate the process of communication in each element (this means that only communicatively valuable phrases are used as replicas, that is, those that can be used in speech, and not generally grammatically correct construction);

7) be economical in time (this means that they must be performed at a normal speech pace, as a result of which a sufficient number of phrases is provided to automate the grammatical form).

Analysis and results

There is a system of conditional speech exercises. They can be classified according to three criteria: by composition, by installations, by the method of execution.

According to the classification of conditional speech exercises according to the way they are performed, four types of conditional speech exercises are distinguished:

Imitative conditional speech exercises are those in which the student, in order to express a certain thought, finds speech units in the necessary forms in the teacher's remark and uses them without changing.

Substitutional conditionally - speech exercises are characterized by the fact that in them there is a substitution of lexical units into the structure of any grammatical form.

Transformational conditionally - speech exercises involve a certain transformation of the cue.

Actually reproductive conditional - speech exercises involve completely independent reproduction in the students' remarks of the grammatical form that was learned in previous exercises.

Therefore, the primary classification for learning is the classification according to the method of execution, since the formation of a skill depends on the actions that the student performs with speech material, and on how he performs them.

Genuine speech refers to exercises in natural communication in various types of speech activity (speaking, listening, reading, and writing). Natural speech communication is the exchange of information motivated by the goals and conditions of learning. In artificial school conditions of mastering a foreign language, this type of exercise is the most creative and most difficult for students, therefore it completes the entire system of exercises and is used to develop speech skills (for example: "Describe the situation shown in the figure", "Listen to the text, comment on the actions of the acting persons", etc.).

The game belongs to speech exercises. It is one of the most effective means of developing grammatical skills.

According to psychologists, the motivation created by the game, that is, the game motivation should be present in the educational process along with communicative, cognitive and aesthetic motivations.

In order to intensify the educational process, increase the level of language proficiency, teachers are actively looking

for means that increase and maintain interest in learning, allowing students to "show themselves", assert themselves, and experience a sense of success.

One way to solve these problems is to use language/speech games. The game is a teaching tool that activates the mental activity of students, makes the learning process attractive and interesting, and makes students worry and worry. This is a powerful incentive to master the language.

Conclusion and recommendations. There are a large number of games that contribute to the formation of grammatical skills.

Grammar games teach students to use samples that contain certain grammatical difficulties. They are used to create a natural situation for the use of a given speech pattern. Grammar games are designed to develop the speech activity and independence of students.

The most productive form of organizing this game is imaginary writing. Students make all sorts of assumptions and then compare with what is written in the letter. The winner is the one whose version matches the "original".

Thus, grammar games ensure the activity of students throughout the lesson, accustom them to systematic work, as a result of which grammatical skills are formed more effectively.

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